

Simulation and Design of Microstrip Antenna for Various Wireless Applications by using SRR's

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Abstract:- Here in this, development and design of microstrip antenna with SRRs (Split Ring Resonator's) are introduced. To reduce size & for improved better performance of introduced antenna SRR's are used. This Metamaterial method used as for designing SRR's for negative permeability. The SRR's are introduced between two substrate layers of Teflon with relative permittivity 4.9. The return loss and VSWR results are better. The return loss of microstrip antenna operating frequency 5.02 Gigahertz is -23 dB, and VSWR is approximately near to 1.15. CST Software is used to obtained for the simulated results of the antenna which having better performance.

Keywords:- SRR's (Split Ring Resonator's), Microstrip antenna, Metamaterial, Permittivity, Size Reduce.

I. INTRODUCTION

At present, Wireless system have grown significantly. Over different wireless services, according to multifunction antennas used to designed for adaptable operations. Also user stipulation indicates the need for reliable, compact, efficient, wireless systems integrating whole receiver & transmitter on single chip [1-2]. The compactness matter of antenna is much important at present. Various design use to reduce patch size in the antenna is iris structure, inserting slot & shorting pin. Due to which, these antennas are designing methods have low performance & complex structures. Currently designed method uses to reduce patch size in antenna are named as SRR's & CSRR's with antennas for better performance & simple structure. Also on other side we can say that with SRR's and CSRR's have a special property which helps for size reduction of proposed antenna [3-4]. Metamaterials used in antennas are exploring scientifically to be the normalized frequency results on electro-magnetic wave propagation. Material used widely is the left handed materials. For the reduction antenna's size with the help of SRR's are introduced in between the substrate layers in this research paper. The introduced antenna take benefits over the past antenna research.

II. METHODOLOGY & DESIGN

The introduced microstrip antenna using substrate Teflon dielectric material with (ϵ_r) relative permittivity 2.1 and height approximately 1.00 mm used by introducing SRR's between the two substrate layers. The dimensions w and l radiates patch which excited by 50Ω (ohm) microstrip feed strip, by using it with quarter wave length transformer for impedance match. The ground patch which used in antenna dimensions are l_t & w_t . By introducing SRR's in antenna that operating frequency 5.02 Gigahertz . The 3D model of antenna optimized by using CST software. In 1999, metamaterial was proposed by Pendry having the negative permeability which is SRR's [5]. The Microstrip antenna and SRR's geometry shown in figures below:

Fig. 1:- Patch Side in antenna

Fig 2:- Ground Side in antenna

Fig. 4:- Structure of SRR's Array in antenna

As in Table no.1, Shows Parametric representation of antenna is given below:

Parameter	Dimension in mm
l_t	40.00
w_t	40.00
l	11.35
w	15.25
l_i	4.90
w_i	0.50
l_j	6.15
w_j	3.50

Table 1:- Parametric Representation of Antenna

Fig. 3:- Design of SRR's

As in Table no. 2, Split Ring Resonator's parametric representation of is given below:

Parameter	Dimension in mm
a	10.00
c	1.00
d	0.50
r	2.50

Table 2:- Parametric Representation of SRR's

In the above figure Structure of SRR's arrays represented in such a way in the antenna.

➤ Return loss:-

The loss of the power in signal reflected/ returned in transmission line or optical fiber by a discontinuity is called Return loss. It is typically expressed as the ratio in dB (decibels),

$$RL (dB) = 20 \log_{10} \frac{SWR}{SWR-1}$$

Where RL stands for return loss in (dB) decibels, and SWR stands for Standing Wave Ratio.

By using the equation, $BW = \left[\frac{f_2 - f_1}{f_c} \right] \times 100\%$, Impedance [8]. return loss which is less than -10 dB can be calculated, in which f_1 stands for lower cut off Frequency, f_2 stands for upper cut off Frequency and f_c stands for center frequency of f_2 and f_1 [8]. The return loss result after simulated characteristics of antenna is -23 dB at 5.02 Gigahertz which is less than the -1.67 dB.

Fig. 5:- Results of Frequency vs Return loss

➤ **VSWR:-**

VSWR stands for Voltage Standing Wave Ratio & its also related to the term Standing Wave Ratio [5]. VSWR is defined as,

$$VSWR = \frac{V_{max}}{V_{min}}$$

The Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) of the introduced antenna is approximately near to 1.15 at 5.02 Gigahertz.

Fig. 6:- Results of VSWR vs Frequency

➤ **Directivity: -**

The maximum value of antenna directive gain is called Directivity. It measures power density in the direction of its strong emission of the antenna radiations.

The Directivity of introduced antenna is 5.02 Gigahertz as results given below:

Fig. 7: Simulated Results of Directivity 6.4 dBi at 5.02 Gigahertz

➤ **Radiation pattern: -**

Directional dependence of the strength of radio waves from the antenna is called as Radiation pattern.

The result of radiation pattern at 5.02 Gigahertz is as given below:

Fig. 8 :- Simulated Pattern Results of Farfield Radiation at 5.02 Gigahertz

III. CONCLUSION

The introduced antenna is simulated and measured for different wireless applications. All the results of the return loss, Farfield radiation & VSWR are given by using the SRR's in the introducing antenna. Due to which it helps to reduce size of antenna. Here substrate used having thickness approximately is 1.00 mm. The simulated results of antennas are return loss with the SRR's is – 23 decibels, the bandwidth for return loss better than 10 decibels and the VSWR of the antenna is nearly to 1.15 in the range of 5-5.5 Gigahertz. As the results compare with VSWR & Return loss are better.

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